

OVERVIEW OF RENEWABLE ENERGY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

The world is rapidly becoming a global village due to the growing daily energy demand of the entire population around the world, while the earth in its form cannot change. There is a growing need for energy and related services to meet human needs for social and economic development, well-being, and health. A return to renewable energy to mitigate the effects of climate change is a great approach that must be sustainable to meet the energy demand of future generations. The study proposed some measures and policy recommendations that, when considered, would help achieve the goal of using renewable energy, thus reducing emissions, mitigating the effects of climate change, and ensuring a clean environment, as well as clean energy for all and the future generations.

1. Introduction

Energy is a need in our daily lives as a way to improve human development, leading to economic growth and productivity. A return to renewable energy sources will help mitigate the effects of climate change — this is a great way, but it must be sustainable to ensure a sustainable future and bequeath to future generations the satisfaction of their energy needs. Knowledge about the relationship between sustainable development and renewable energy, in particular, remains limited.

As you know, in the sustainable development of any country, the consumption of fuel and energy resources is a determining factor. Since a certain amount of energy is spent on the production of each type of product, that is, the cost of each unit of production will also directly depend on the consumption of heat and electricity.

2. Main Part

One of the most important conditions for the development of mankind, of course, is the use of energy. The availability of usable energy has always been considered a necessary factor to meet human needs, prolong human life, and improve living conditions.

In our modern life, energy is the basis for the development of industries, which determines the level of production growth. The pace of development of the energy sector in all industrialized countries should outstrip the development of other industries. The reason is that the energy supply of each country is one of the main conditions for its socio-economic development and independence.

At the same time, energy is one of the sources of negative impact on the environment and human health. It has a corresponding impact on the atmosphere (oxygen consumption, the release of harmful vapors, moisture and solids), the

hydrosphere (water use, the creation of artificial reservoirs, the release of hot and polluted water and liquid waste), the biosphere (the release of its toxic substances) and the lithosphere (the consumption of fossil fuels, landscape changes).

Uzbekistan has a well-developed electric power system. According to the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of 01.11.2019, the population is 33800610 people. The demand for electricity is more than 69 billion kWh. There are more than 30 power plants with a total capacity of more than 14,000 MW in the republic. According to statistics, by 2030, the demand for electricity in our country will amount to 117 billion kWh.

Uzbekistan has a huge potential of various renewable energy resources: hydropower, solar energy, wind energy, biofuels, etc. Therefore, there is a favorable opportunity to develop the use of various electrical installations based on non-traditional and renewable energy sources, including for energy supply to consumers in remote, not covered by centralized power lines, and not connected to the system in rural areas.

The huge potential of all renewable energy sources is an important foundation for the successful development of renewable energy sources. Creating a favorable economic climate in Uzbekistan will allow us to master a significant part of this technical potential.

In market conditions, there are three main reasons for the need for widespread use of renewable energy sources:

The first is National Energy Security, because due to the depletion of minerals such as oil, gas, coal, renewable energy sources are the source of energy within the country, and the above type of fuel reduces consumption.

The second is the potential risk caused by climate change. While a renewable energy source helps meet energy needs, it also reduces greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere.

Third, the decline in the cost of some alternative energy sources over the past ten years. The reduction in the cost of alternative energy sources can be explained by the fact that the technology of its production is being improved. As the industry evolves, costs will fall even further.

In the second decade of the new century, clean energy technologies are changing the

energy supply of our homes, businesses, and vehicles. Even more drastic changes may occur in the coming decades, decades, as the pace of clean energy use and global market development accelerates. Despite the fact that significant funds are initially spent on the use of installations from renewable energy sources, they are economically justified. Due to the energy generated by conventional fuel, the oxides of sulfur, nitrogen, and carbon released into the air are carried over long distances. In addition, they negatively affect the plants, the soil, falling on the ground as part of precipitation. As a result of the excess of such acids in the environment, heavy metals enter the food and, ultimately, through these products affect the human body. In this case, one damage also causes a second damage. Renewable energy sources that are environmentally friendly do not harm the environment. I must say that these resources are usually insufficient for the full provision of settlements and large industrial enterprises. They provide energy to remote villages, neighborhoods, and small objects.

3. Conclusion

Summing up, we can say that the priority of using alternative and renewable energy sources in our country is not only an inexhaustible source of energy, but also the possibility of generating electricity in an environmentally friendly way without polluting the environment.

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